

Hydrogen sulfide, a gasocrine signal, is likely sensed via gasoreceptors

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

Running title: H₂S-sensing gasoreceptors

Keywords: Hydrogen sulfide sensing

DRAFT
#gasocrine

Understanding how organisms communicate is a fundamental question in biology and marks an evolutionarily important milestone. Organisms largely communicate via gas-based gasocrine, light-based photocrine, sound-based sonocrine, mineral/metal-based metallochrine, water-based aquacrine, and thermal radiation-based thermocrine signaling. Due to the importance of gasocrine signaling for biotic life, how organisms can sense gasocrine signals such as O₂ (oxygen) directly via O₂-sensing protein gasoreceptors (or sensors) has been largely investigated in microorganisms. Even though H₂S (hydrogen sulfide) is also one of the gasocrine signals, to the best of my knowledge and a few other leading experts on sulfide sensing and H₂S-dependent signaling, how organisms sense H₂S *per se* is still unknown. In my opinion, as H₂S has been demonstrated to bind to Zn²⁺ and Cu²⁺ in vestimentiferan tubeworms hemoglobin, Cu/Zn superoxide dismutase respectively, other H₂S-binding Zn²⁺- and Cu²⁺-based metalloproteins with signaling domains are likely putative H₂S-sensing gasoreceptors H₂S. I also wonder if H₂S is the antagonist of hemoglobin, which I previously proposed as a putative aquareceptor. Understanding how cells sense H₂S or other gases via gasoreceptors may help us better understand the general principles underlying human diseases.